

A STUDY OF THE NATURE OF THE AQUEOUS LAYER AFTER EXTRACTION OF THE ETHERIAL BLUE PEROXYCHROMIC ACID

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Blue peroxychromic acid was prepared by taking constant volumes of 4% chromic acid solution and ether, and varying amounts of 20 vol. hydrogen peroxide were added. The ethereal peroxychromic acid was separated by means of a separating funnel. The aqueous layer was investigated by taking 10 c.c. of the solution in a weighed silica crucible, evaporating on a water-bath and igniting. Another 10 c.c. of the solution was iodimetrically titrated against a standard hypo solution. From 10 c.c. of the solution chromium hydroxide was precipitated by means of a dilute NaOH solution, washed and ignited. From the results the aqueous layer has been found to be chromium chromate which appears to be suspended in solution from which it is precipitated after a week or so.

During the study of the constitution and the chemical properties of the blue peroxychromic acid Berthelot (*Compt. rend.*, 1889, 108, 477) observed the formation of a brown substance with weaker acids and potassium dichromate and hydrogen peroxide. The phenomenon was found to be more pronounced when hydrogen peroxide was added to an aqueous solution of potassium dichromate. A brown substance was found to be formed with effervescence, and after sometime the brown substance was decomposed and the liquid again attained the colour of the solution of potassium dichromate. The solution neither contained reduced chromic oxide nor hydrogen peroxide. The brown compound was considered to be probably a loose compound of hydrogen peroxide with chromic oxide. It decomposes rapidly with generation of chromic acid, liberation of oxygen and formation of water. The brown colour of the unstable intermediate product points to the formation of chromium chromate. The hydrogen peroxide oxidises the chromium chromate, forming chromic acid and water.

Bobtelsky, Glasner and Bobtelsky (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 966) during the study of catalytic decomposition of hydrogen peroxide with chromic acid by the method of absorption of light, are of the view that during the above reaction two compounds are formed- one, the blue and the other, violet or brown. They did not make any attempt to study the nature of the two compounds, simultaneously formed during the reaction of chromic acid and hydrogen peroxide. It is a well-known fact that the blue substance can be extracted with ether, and it is known as blue peroxychromic acid. Since no attempt is reported to have been made to study the nature of the aqueous layer, an investigation has been made to ascertain the nature of the aqueous layer after the separation of the blue peroxychromic acid by means of ether.

EXPERIMENTAL

When hydrogen peroxide is added to a chromic acid solution and ether, the blue peroxychromic acid formed goes into the ethereal layer which is separated by means of a separating funnel. The aqueous layer, which is left over, does not possess

the coloration of the chromic acid, but attains a brown colour. When to a portion of this brown solution a sodium hydroxide solution is added, a green precipitate of chromium hydroxide is formed, which indicates that chromium is present in the basic part of the compound in the aqueous layer. If to the other portion of the above solution acetic acid and lead acetate solutions are added, a yellow precipitate of lead chromate is formed which indicates that chromate is also present in the above solution. In order to investigate the nature of the aqueous layer, the solution was obtained by keeping 100 c.c. of a 4% chromic acid solution in a Jena bottle in ice till the temperature of the solution attained that of ice. To this solution 100 c.c. of ice-cooled ether was added and to this mixture ice cooled solution of 2.5N hydrogen peroxide was added in varying amounts (10 to 200 c.c.), keeping the volumes of chromic acid solution and ether constant. The blue peroxychromic acid formed was separated by means of a separating funnel and the aqueous layer was taken in a separate Jena bottle and was left for about 24 hours in order that any unchanged hydrogen peroxide might be decomposed. The decomposition of hydrogen peroxide was ensured by the fact that on acidification of the solution, no blue peroxychromic acid was formed.

From the aqueous layer a 10 c.c. portion was taken in a weighed silica crucible, evaporated on a water-bath, ignited to convert it into Cr_2O_3 , cooled in a desiccator and weighed. Another 10 c.c. portion of the same solution was titrated iodimetrically against a standard thiosulphate solution. A third 10 c.c. portion from the same solution was taken in a beaker and precipitated as chromium hydroxide by means of a dilute sodium hydroxide solution, filtered through a gravimetric filter paper, washed free of NaOH and chromate ions, dried and ignited in a weighed silica crucible, and the weight determined. Thus, the weight of Cr_2O_3 corresponding to the amount of chromium in the basic portion of the compound was found. From the volumetric results the amount of substance present as chromate in 10 c.c. of the solution was calculated. The results are tabulated below.

TABLE I

From 10 c.c. of the aqueous layer.

H_2O_2 added.	$\text{Cr}_2(\text{CrO}_4)_3$.	Cr_2O_3 .	Ratio $\frac{\text{Cr}_2(\text{CrO}_4)_3}{\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3}$	H_2O_2 added.	$\text{Cr}_2(\text{CrO}_4)_3$ layer.	Cr_2O_3 .	Ratio $\frac{\text{Cr}_2(\text{CrO}_4)_3}{\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3}$
10 c.c.	0.3731 g.	0.2212 g.	1.60	90 c.c.	0.1791 g.	0.1520 g.	1.17
20	0.2711	0.2273	1.19	100	0.1636	0.1382	1.18
30	0.2274	0.1878	1.20	110	0.1575	0.1346	1.17
40	0.1917	0.1624	1.17	120	0.1321	0.1196	1.10
50	0.1428	0.1246	1.15	140	0.1044	0.0994	1.05
60	0.1666	0.1428	1.15	160	0.1107	0.0982	1.05
65	0.1422	0.1262	1.13	180	0.0930	0.0582	1.06
80	0.1404	0.1248	1.12	200	0.0992	0.0984	1.05

When the amount of chromium oxide obtained from two molecules of chromium chromate is calculated, it is found to be as follows :

i. e., 904 g. of chromium chromate on heating affords 760 g. of chromic oxide. Therefore, the ratio between the weight of two molecules of chromium chromate and chromic oxide obtained from two molecules of chromium chromate is 904 : 760 as 1.189 : 1.

It is quite evident from the above table that except the first ratio, all the rest are fairly constant within the limits of experimental error. Most of the ratios obtained in the above table are in fair agreement with the ratio calculated on theoretical grounds.

The high and low values of the ratios can be explained. The high value is on account of the fact that when the amount of the hydrogen peroxide added is less than the corresponding volume of chromic acid taken, some chromic acid is left unchanged and the oxidation value is high, thus, yielding the ratios high. When hydrogen peroxide is added in large excess, some of it is left unchanged and goes with the aqueous layer. This unchanged hydrogen peroxide reduces chromate ions to trivalent chromium state, thus providing oxidation values low, which yields a low ratio.

TABLE II

H_2O_2 .	Total Cr_2O_3 , Cr_2O_3 by pptn. (From 10 c.c. of the solution).		Ratio of II/III.	H_2O_2 .	Total Cr_2O_3 , Cr_2O_3 by pptn. (From 10 c.c. of the solution).		Ratio of II/III.
	(II)	(III)			(II)	(III)	
20 c.c.	0.2272 g.	0.0804 g.	2.80	100 c.c.	0.1382 g.	0.0514 g.	2.60
30	0.1878	0.0648	2.80	110	0.1346	0.0540	2.49
40	0.1625	0.0630	2.57	120	0.1196	0.0472	2.50
50	0.1256	0.0520	2.40	140	0.1000	0.0450	2.20
60	0.1416	0.0602	2.40	160	0.1052	0.0842	2.10
70	0.1294	0.0525	2.40	180	0.0820	0.0420	2.10
80	0.1292	0.0564	2.30	200	0.0890	0.0444	2.00
90	0.1510	0.0572	2.60				

When two molecules of chromium chromate are precipitated by means of dilute solution of sodium hydroxide, the reaction is represented by the equation :

Further, when chromium hydroxide is ignited it is obtained as :

i. e., the total weight of chromium oxide obtained from two molecules of chromic chromate is 760 g., and when precipitated, the weight of Cr_2O_3 is 304 g. Therefore the ratio between the total chromium oxide and the chromic oxide obtained from the basic part of the chromium is 760 : 304 as 2.5 : 1.

From Table II it is quite evident that most of the results are between 2.40 and 2.60, which are in fair agreement with the theoretical results calculated. The first few results are higher; the reason is that on account of less amount of hydrogen peroxide added, the whole of the chromic acid taken is not completely acted upon, thus the value for the oxide obtained by the precipitation method is less. In the last portion

of the table the ratios are lower. The reason is that on account of too much excess of hydrogen peroxide, some of the chromate ions are reduced to hydrated chromic oxide which comes down as a precipitate of chromium hydroxide when NaOH is added. Thus, the amount of precipitated chromic hydroxide increases and it lowers the ratio.

It is clear from the above results that it is very likely that when the blue peroxy-chromic acid has been extracted out, the aqueous layer contains chromium chromate. When the layer is left for more than a week, it is precipitated.

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